

STUDY OF METHODS FOR DETERMINING ANTIBIOTICS IN MILK AND DAIRY PRODUCTS

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Abstract. *In this work, we conducted a comparative study of methods for determining antibiotics in milk and dairy products, ensuring uniformity of measurements and characteristics and measurement errors.*

Keywords: *antibiotic, penicillin, streptomycin, chloramphenicol, milk, Delvotest.*

Introduction

The presence of residual amounts of antibiotics in raw milk represents, on the one hand, a threat to consumer health, and on the other a technological risk in the production of dairy products. Monitoring residual antibiotics in raw milk is mandated by the sanitary legislation of most countries. European legislation is among the strictest in this regard: for the vast majority of antibiotics actually used in livestock farming, maximum residue limits (MRLs) are established, and control procedures are standardized.

According to EU Directive 92/46, the procedure for establishing maximum residue limits must be carried out “using validated, scientifically justified methods regulated, in particular, at the EU or international level.” As for arbitration methods, the directive refers to Commission Decision No. 91/180, which describes them in detail. The arbitration methods are divided into qualitative methods for detecting antibiotics and methods for determining the presence and concentration of penicillin group antibiotics. The requirements for the sensitivity of these methods are also specified.

Among international standards recognized in the EU are validated AOAC International proprietary methods, such as Delvotest (DSM, Netherlands), SNAP (Idexx Inc., USA), Charm II (Charm Sciences Inc., USA), as well as certain national standards for example, the German LMBG standards for chromatographic methods for determining antibiotics in food products, including milk. The International Organization for Standardization (ISO) and the International Dairy Federation (IDF) do not standardize the detailed testing procedure for antibiotics, but rather the description of the method, based on which a well-founded conclusion can be drawn about the compliance of the method with the required performance characteristics [1].

The Russian Sanitary Regulations SanPiN 2.3.2.1078-01 establish a complete prohibition of residual amounts of penicillin, streptomycin, chloramphenicol, and tetracycline group antibiotics in raw milk, noting in a footnote the required detection limits for the methods used. As analysis methods, SanPiN 2.3.2.1078-01 allows for “metrologically certified methods that meet the requirements for ensuring measurement uniformity and measurement error characteristics, as well as their suitability for use in testing product samples and monitoring their parameters, and also methods that meet these requirements and are approved in accordance with established procedures,” but without providing direct references to documents that set out the procedure for certification and approval.

On the other hand, the reference appendix to SanPiN lists several methodological guidelines for determining residual antibiotics in food products, including milk, and references GOST 23454-79 for methods for determining inhibitors in milk (which is also cited in GOST R 52054-2003 “Natural Raw Cow’s Milk. Technical Conditions”). In addition, there is GOST 51600-2000 “Milk. Method for Determining Antibiotics,” which roughly corresponds to the EU arbitration method. In general, the Russian standards for the content of residual antibiotics and methods for their control are similar to the European ones, but they are prescribed in a much less clear and comprehensive manner [2].

The processes of Russia’s integration into the global economy objectively require the harmonization of approaches to product quality assessment. The emerging new technical regulatory framework in Russia in particular, the Technical Regulation for milk and dairy products is largely aligned with European legislation. The aim of our study was to assess Russian standard and proprietary methods for determining antibiotic residues in terms of their adequacy to both domestic and European standards, based on ISO 13969 (IDF 183) Milk and Milk Products — Guidelines for the Standard Description of Bacterial Inhibition Tests and ISO 18330 (IDF 188) Milk and Milk Products - Guidelines for the Standardized Description of Immunological Bacterial Receptor Assays for the Detection of Antimicrobial Substance Residues [3, 4, 5].

Materials and Methods

As inhibitor-free milk, we used raw milk from one of the suburban farms in the Almaty region, verified for the absence of inhibitors in accordance with GOST 23454-79, for antibiotics according to GOST 51600-2000, as well as by the Charm II method.

In addition to the main antibiotic groups (penicillin and tetracycline), we tested the most commonly used antibiotics for treating mastitis amoxicillin, cloxacillin, and chlortetracycline in concentrations ranging from 4 to 0.25 of the EU MRL.

Standard dilutions of penicillin and tetracycline antibiotics (produced in Russia) and commercial preparations of amoxicillin, cloxacillin, oxytetracycline, and chlortetracycline (KRKA, Slovenia) were introduced into the milk. The dilutions were prepared according to MU3049-84 Methodological Guidelines for Determining Residual Amounts of Antibiotics in Livestock Products and were serially diluted to working concentrations of 0.016; 0.008; 0.004; 0.002; 0.001 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^3$ (units/g) for penicillin and amoxicillin; 0.1; 0.05; 0.025; 0.012; 0.006 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^3$ (units/g) for cloxacillin; and 0.5; 0.25; 0.12; 0.06; 0.03 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^3$ (units/g) for tetracycline group antibiotics. In addition, when determining the number of positive results, a negative control was used alongside the raw native milk specifically, the SKIV preparation (according to GOST 23454-79), produced by Biokompass LLC.

Each concentration of every antibiotic, as well as the negative controls, was tested in five replicates using each of the investigated methods. The following methods and test kits were used in the study to determine residual amounts of antibiotics:

- MU 3049-84 Methodological Guidelines for Determining Residual Amounts of Antibiotics in Livestock Products (hereinafter MU-84);
- MUK 4.2.026-95 Express Method for Determining Antibiotics in Food Products;
- GOST 51600-2000 Milk. Methods for Determining Antibiotics. Plate method with *Bacillus stearothermophilus* (hereinafter Bac. stear.);
- GOST 51600-2000. Method with bromocresol purple indicator (hereinafter Delvotest);

- Draft Amendment No. 1 to GOST 51600-2000. Method with 3,3,5,5-trimethylbenzidine and dimethyl sulfoxide (hereinafter SNAP);
- Test kit Blue-Yellow produced by Charm Sciences Inc., USA (hereinafter Charm BY);
- Test kit Charm MRL produced by Charm Sciences Inc., USA;
- Test kit Charm II produced by Charm Sciences Inc., USA.

MUK-95, Bac. stear., Delvotest, and Charm BY are qualitative methods based on inhibition of bacterial growth and do not differentiate the type of inhibitor. MU-84, which is also based on inhibition of bacterial growth, is a quantitative method that allows for the identification of the antibiotic type. SNAP, Charm MRL, and Charm II are immunological (bacterial) receptor-based antibiotic-specific methods; among them, SNAP and Charm MRL are qualitative, while Charm II is a semi-quantitative method.

Since five out of the eight tested methods belong to the category of bacterial growth inhibition tests, the presentation of the results was based on ISO 13969:2003 (IDF 183).

The following indicators were determined:

1. Limit of detection with 95% probability (LOD 95%) this is the antibiotic concentration at which the given method produces 95% positive results. Equivocal results were always treated as negative. The LOD 95% was determined graphically: points on a graph showing the percentage of positive results (Y-axis) at a given antibiotic concentration (X-axis) were connected by a line. The projection onto the X-axis of the intersection point of this curve with the 95% line was taken as the LOD 95% value.

2. Ratio of LOD 95% to MRL. This ratio indicates how well the method aligns with the established Maximum Residue Limit (MRL): overly sensitive methods will produce positive results even at permissible concentrations, while insufficiently sensitive methods will fail to detect residues at unacceptable levels.

3. Percentage of false positive results.

Results and Discussion

All methods, except for MUK-95, demonstrated linearity of results and a direct dependence of the number of positive results on the antibiotic concentration. MUK-95 did not yield 100% positive nor 100% negative results for any tested concentration of any of the antibiotics, including negative controls. Therefore, MUK-95 was excluded from further study, and thus its feasibility for detecting residual antibiotics in raw milk is called into question. Figures 1 and 2 present the graphs for determining the LOD 95% for amoxicillin and oxytetracycline; the table shows the LOD 95% for the seven methods across the six tested antibiotics.

Table 1.

Antibiotic, µg/kg	Detection limits of antibiotics by investigated methods						
	MU-84	Bac.stear.	SNAP	Charm MRL	Charm II	Delvotest	Charm BY
Penicillin	6	7	3	3	1,7	3,5	3,7
Amoxicillin	7,4	6,8	6	3,5	1,6	6	6,8
Cloxacillin	94	96	42	24	22	45	48
Tetracycline	95	200	30	95	28	420	225
Oxytetracycline	95	225	30	95	28	420	230
Chlortetracycline	90	185	30	94	28	215	175

The lowest detection limits were demonstrated by the specific methods: SNAP, Charm MRL, and Charm II. For beta-lactam antibiotics, Charm MRL and Charm II showed the highest sensitivity, while for the tetracycline group, SNAP and Charm II were more sensitive. Among the bacterial growth inhibition methods, the most sensitive for beta-lactams were Delvotest and Charm BY, and for tetracyclines MU-84. It should be noted that none of the tested methods meets the detection limits for tetracyclines specified by SanPiN 2.3.2.1078-01 (which requires detection limits 10 times lower than the EU MRL).

Conclusion. All the tested methods (except MUK-95) proved capable of reliably detecting penicillin at levels required by SanPiN 2.3.2.1078-01. However, none of the methods reliably and consistently detects tetracyclines at the level specified by this regulation.

REFERENCES

1. Bannikova L.A., Koroleva N.S., Semenikhina V.F. Microbiological Foundations of Dairy Production. Moscow: Agropromizdat, 2007.
2. Töpel A. Chemistry and Physics of Milk. Moscow: Food Industry, 2009.
3. Bannikova L.A., Koroleva N.S. Microbiological Foundations of Dairy Production. Handbook. Moscow: Agropromizdat, 2001.
4. Töpel A. Chemistry and Physics of Milk. Moscow: Food Industry, 2000.
5. D.M. Yunusov. Brucellosis Disease and Its Prevention. In: Issues of Innovative Development of Science, Education, and Technology. International Scientific-Practical Conference, Andijan, April 12, 2022.